

D6.3 NON-INVASIVE PROCESSES FOR DIGITAL TWIN-BASED SAFETY MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

In our research, we have developed a framework that enhances traditional safety measures with digital technologies. This framework allows for the coexistence and mutual support of physical and digital twins, providing stakeholders in the construction process with decision-making tools to enhance on-site safety.

In this report, we demonstrate how to integrate construction safety into the design phase using virtual reality (VR). We provide an example of what digital onboarding might entail, ensuring that all workers, regardless of their language preference, possess adequate knowledge before entering the site. Additional applications include the detection of personnel in risk zones, identification of individuals on-site outside of working hours (in collaboration with WP3), and protective gear verification, among others. Further, we show

how to aggregate data on health and safety behaviour towards site specific and company specific safety culture indicators.

Lastly, we conducted a series of interviews to gain insights into the current perceptions, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of digital technologies on construction sites. This information is crucial for understanding how these technologies can be effectively implemented to improve safety and efficiency in the construction industry, and at the same time ensure personal integrity.

KEYWORDS

Digital twin, construction industry, safety, real-time safety technology, technology adoption, challenges

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ACRONYMS & DEFINITIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interfaces
AR	Augmented Reality
BIM	Building Information Modeling
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy technology
CII	Construction Industry Institute
CPS	Cyber-physical system
DT	Digital Technologies
GAN	Generative Adversarial Networks
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System, refers to a constellation of satellites providing signals from space that transmit positioning and timing data to GNSS receivers. The receivers then use this data to determine location.
H&S	Health and Safety
IFC	International Foundation Class, is a way to exchange files between different software programs
IMU	Inertial measurement unit – a device that typically consists of gyroscopes to measure and report angular rate and accelerometers
IoT	Internet of Things
LGBM	Light Gradient Boosting Machine
MR	Mixed Reality
RFID	Radio-frequency identification
UWB	Ultra-wideband, a radio technology that can use a very low energy level for short-range, high bandwidth communications over a large portion of the radio spectrum
VCS	Virtual Construction Simulation
VDC	Virtual Design and Construction
VR	Virtual Reality

ASHVIN PROJECT

ASHVIN aims at enabling the European construction industry to significantly improve its productivity, while reducing cost and ensuring absolutely safe work conditions, by providing a proposal for a European wide digital twin standard, an open source digital twin platform integrating IoT and image technologies, and a set of tools and demonstrated procedures to apply the platform and the standard proven to guarantee specified productivity, cost, and safety improvements. The envisioned platform will provide a digital representation of the construction product at hand and allow to collect real-time digital data before, during, and after production of the product to continuously monitor changes in the environment and within the production process. Based on the platform, ASHVIN will develop and demonstrate applications that use the digital twin data. These applications will allow it to fully leverage the potential of the IoT based digital twin platform to reach the expected impacts (better scheduling forecast by 20%; better allocation of resources and optimization of equipment usage; reduced number of accidents; reduction of construction projects). The ASHVIN solutions will overcome worker protection and privacy issues that come with the tracking of construction activities, provide means to fuse video data and sensor data, integrate geo-monitoring data, provide multi-physics simulation methods for digital representing the behaviour of a product (not only its shape), provide evidence-based engineering methods to design for productivity and safety, provide 4D simulation and visualization methods of construction processes, and develop a lean planning process supported by real-time data. All innovations will be demonstrated on real-world construction projects across Europe. The ASHVIN consortium combines strong R&I players from 9 EU member states with strong expertise in construction and engineering management, digital twin technology, IoT, and data security / privacy.

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1 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable report is part of Work Package (WP) 6 of the ASHVIN project titled "Social innovation, and standardization".

The objectives of WP6 are to determine future trajectories of ASHVIN developed innovations, including standardization triggering standards to be applied by the market in connection with the deployment of new innovative privacy focused practices within the industry. These will enable the project results to be widely used afterwards, thus ensuring a sustainable impact of the project in the long run. The task of T6.3 focuses on determining innovative solutions that enhance and preserve worker data and privacy while increasing effective reductions in workplace risks and partly builds, and should be read together, on findings in T6.5 and T1.4.

1.1 Background

The construction industry is an important part of Europe's economy, accounting for 18 million jobs and contributing to almost 9% of the GDP (European Commission, 2021). While the sector offers a lot of employment opportunities, the unique characteristics in construction industry such as dynamic environment, change in composition of crews, materials, equipment, challenging work environment and culture make it one of the most high-risk industries and is a leading contributor of fatalities and accidents at work. In 2021, more than one fifth (22.1 %) of all fatal accidents at work in the EU took place within the construction sector, making it the most high-risk industry in terms of fatal accidents (in absolute numbers) (Eurostat, 2023). For the same year, the highest incidence of non-fatal accidents at work in the EU was observed in construction, with 3 152 such accidents per 100 000 persons employed. It is worth noting that the rate of accidents and fatalities in construction varies widely across different countries and regions within Europe. Nevertheless, the overall trend indicates that construction is a high-risk industry that requires continued efforts to improve safety and reduce the number of accidents and fatalities.

The situation is not acceptable and ECTP (2023) notes that "New technologies such as AI, IoT, and automation in on-site and off-site production need to be integrated faster to existing industrial processes to enable performance gains, at various levels, such as workers' safety on construction sites, resources efficiency and their long-term use/reuse, user experience and comfort, asset management.". However, the construction industry has fallen behind in terms of adoption of new technologies, particularly in the construction phase (JRC, 2019). The construction sector is one of the least digitized sectors in the European Union (European Commission, 2021).

1.2 Purpose and intended audience

The high injury rate in the construction sector is one of the sector's biggest issues. Digitalization advancements have provided novel opportunities to augment safety protocols within the construction industry. This is facilitated through establishing a connected construction site where various devices and systems are interconnected and can interact. This integrated technology can identify potential hazards and triggering alerts, thereby playing a crucial role in incident minimization and prevention

on the construction site. In this study, the focus was on real-time safety technologies in the construction industry. The objective of this study was to facilitate acceleration of the use and implementation of real-time safety technologies in the construction industry, which included understanding the attitude and perspectives of industry professionals towards these technologies.

This deliverable aims to provide the reader with:

1. An understanding of how the digital solutions could complement and enhance current H&S work.
2. A framework for these solutions.
3. Examples on the elements of the framework.

This deliverable can benefit any reader associated with construction works, whether in the early design phase or the construction phase, who wants to increase safety on site. It also can act as an inspiration for software developers who are planning to provide secure IoT data collection and data fusion methods from multiple sources and develop digital twin solutions for construction sites, whether they are general digital twin platforms or particular applications for utilizing IoT data, to better understand the needs and perceptions of site personnel.

1.3 Outline of the report

This document is structured into 11 chapters. The first section presents the background and the objective of the deliverable report. Chapter 2 explains in more detail the problems of the construction industry and the potential of digital technologies - in particular related to a digital twin - for solving them. In Chapter 3, the framework for H&S is presented. In chapters 4 to 8, the elements of the framework are presented in detail. Chapter 9 discusses the results, and Chapter 10 proposes some conclusions.

1.4 Methodology

The deliverable is based on desk research, mainly consisting of white papers and scientific papers, the ASHVIN deliverable 1.5, and a literature survey. Furthermore, two master thesis works, supervised by the ASHVIN partners PlanB and NCC, respectively, have been completed within the scope of this study: Stenbäck Juhrich (2023), and Huseynli and Tasnim (2023). The work has also been supplemented by interviews with actors within and outside the ASHVIN consortium. Finally, some unique examples have been developed for ASHVIN regarding improved safety on site which are presented.

2 LITERATURE SURVEY

This section aims to provide an overview of the current state of knowledge on safety in construction and the application of digital technologies for safety in the construction industry. The reviewed literature includes research on the possibilities and applications of different technologies for improving safety on construction sites, as well as studies on the individual and organizational factors that influence the adoption of technologies. Additionally, the literature also covers the issues of privacy and integrity that arise with the implementation of monitoring technologies at workplaces.

2.1 Safety In Construction and Possibilities of Technical Solutions

The aim of the literature survey was to frame existing knowledge related to digitalization and safety in construction, see Appendix A for typical literature references. Many authors note the possibilities with digitalization, for example, “With the development of monitoring technique, the traditional manual monitoring and management methods are no longer suitable for the study of construction safety” (Ye et al, 2023), and that “The use of real-time 3D visualization and geometric proximity monitoring has key advantages over other methods, especially when considering a construction jobsite” (Talmaki, and Kamat, 2022).

The prerequisites of a construction are that it is a dynamic workplace that is constantly changing, this leads to dangers arising due to these conditions and workers must constantly manage these different risks that arise (Wang and Razavi, 2016). Safety management is key to reducing human related risks, human risk factors can be tackled through training and appropriate use of safety devices and inspections (Zhang et al., 2019). Traditional safety management is about training and that workers are informed of risks associated with work activities beforehand, *i.e.*, they must rely on previous experience and skills to handle both identified and unidentified hazards and adapt their behavior accordingly. Workers' ability in dangerous situations is influenced by both human and contextual factors, such as, their awareness of safety, motivation, time pressure, peer pressure, etc. This means that the workers' ability to detect hazards varies greatly depending on where they are and whether something or someone around them poses a danger to their safety (Guo et al., 2017b). Further, accidents tend to happen when workers are subjected to unforeseen risks and lack focus or awareness at the same time. Therefore, utilizing technology to detect hazards and immediately warning employees can empower them to change their actions and prevent serious accidents (Guo et al., 2017b).

The German Social Accident Insurance shows that the most common causes of fatal accidents on German construction sites are caused by falls (30% of the accidents), vehicles and heavy equipment (13%), falling objects (8%) and accidents with tools and machines (DGUV, 2020). A similar trend can be found in Sweden where the accident types show a rather complex and scattered pattern: body movement with physical overload (18%), injuries from tools and gear (16%), collapse, falls and rupture of material (12%), falls from a height (12%) and falls at the same level (tripping) (12%). In the U.S., according to data from the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics, falls account for 21% of all accident-causing factors, followed by heavy machinery and vehicles (8%), falling objects (13%) and accident-causing substances (15%) (OSHA, 2019). The

Occupational Safety & Health Administration (OSHA) states that falls are the leading cause of death in the construction sector in the US, and falls cause one of every three construction worker's deaths (OSHA, n.d.a).

2.2 Sensor Technologies for Safety in Construction

IoT is utilized in various sensors to monitor workers and hazardous situations at the construction site and can monitor multiple safety parameters (Wang et al., 2022). Wearable technology involves different sensors which are worn on clothes, equipment or body parts and can be used for on-site monitoring and positioning, fall detection, real-time proximity detection, warnings system, and hazard zone identification (Awolusi et al., 2018). According to JRC (2019) implementing wearable solutions in the construction sites could have a huge impact on improving the safety for workers at construction sites. The development of various sensing technologies has contributed to the evolvement of real-time locating and proximity warning systems which can be applied on construction to increase safety (Wang & Razavi, 2016).

The challenge when applying sensors for monitoring workers is the complex and constantly changing construction site environment and multiple obstacles such as the building, formwork, equipment, and workers, which can cause signal blockage due to non-line of sight conditions, signal attenuation, signal shadowing, diffraction, scattering or multipath propagation which makes it challenging to position and monitor assets (Li et al., 2020). Further, a noisy environment with limited power supply and presence of electrical and metallic material are other challenges present at the construction site which can interfere with the technology (Li et al., 2020). Finally, privacy and integrity aspects need to be considered. These will be further discussed in 2.3.

Chae and Yoshida (2010) used an active radio-frequency identification (RFID) transponder for a safety management system to prevent collision between equipment and workers at an outdoor construction site. The RFID system was used to compute the working areas and the positioning of workers and equipment. If the workers were too close to any equipment, they received a proximity warning from the system. However, in the outdoor environment the positioning accuracy and precision of the outdoor RFID system was low, mainly as the result due to range and shielding (Chae and Yoshida, 2010). Teizer (2015) used passive RFID tags attached to workers' hard hats for proximity detection and warning system to prevent collisions between equipment and workers at an outdoor construction site. Similarly, as in the aforementioned study, the positioning accuracy and precision were low.

In a study by Huang et al. (2021), a system using Bluetooth (BLE) was attached to construction workers' hard hats and equipment to monitor dangerous proximity between workers and equipment in real time on an outdoor construction site. The system evaluated the proximity by monitoring the movement of the workers and equipment and issued a vibro-tactile warning to the worker if they were deemed too close. Accident information such as the time, worker and equipment ID, position, and distance, was recorded on a cloud database to generate safety reports when hazardous situations occurred. Each worker had two positioning tags, and each equipment had three tags, and nine sensors were installed across the construction site.

However, the study faced challenges with low positioning accuracy due to metal interference, and errors and missing data due to the wireless connectivity of the server and sensors.

In a study by Chan et al. (2020), a proximity warning system at construction sites was developed to incorporate workers' awareness. The system used GPS to locate workers and equipment, IMUs (inertial measurement unit) for head orientation, and ultra-wideband (UWB) technology to alert workers of hazards outside their field of view. By factoring in workers' field of view while generating a proximity warning, the system was able to decrease the number of false alarms triggered in safe conditions.

Li et al. (2015) conducted a study where a virtual construction simulation system (VCS) in conjunction with a real-time location system was used. The VCS was utilized to simulate a construction site with predefined hazardous areas. The positions of workers and equipment were continuously monitored and transmitted to the VCS in real-time, when a worker is situated near a hazardous area, a warning is sent to the workers and the incident is reported and saved in the system for future training.

2.3 Digitally monitoring the construction site

The risks associated with different construction activities depend on available resources such as material and tools, in construction these risks are highly influenced by other temporal and spatial conditions such as location, duration, and other construction activities carried out simultaneously. Thus, monitoring the construction environment, heavy equipment and associated risk factors is significant in terms of increasing the safety of construction workers (Choe and Leite, 2020). Monitoring the construction environment can be divided into static monitoring which refers to targets with a constant position, and dynamic monitoring which refers to targets in motion such as heavy equipment and moving vehicles (Guo et al., 2017a). For proximity detection systems, dynamic monitoring of vehicles and heavy equipment becomes crucial. Sensing technologies such as GNSS (Global Navigation Satellite System) technologies or radio frequency based technologies such as RFID tags or UWB technology are mainly used for monitoring dynamic environments (Guo et al., 2017a). UWB technology can be used to track crane movements and pose estimation which can be utilized for collision avoidance by construction site crane operators (Zhang et al., 2012). Similarly, Siddiqui et al. (2019) used a UWB system in an outdoor construction site to track heavy equipment, the researchers recommended fusing data from complimentary sensory data source, e.g. video, to further enhance the accuracy of the system. Montaser and Moselhi (2014) used low cost Ultra high frequency passive RFID tags and readers for indoor locating of workers and material tracking near real-time at a construction site. Cheng et al. (2017) developed an audio-based system to analyze the activity and tracking construction equipment. Audio data was captured from microphones installed at the construction site; machine learning was used to analyze the data.

There exist several studies showing promising results in using vision-based methods for real-time position estimation of heavy construction equipment. Soltani et al. (2018) presented a method based on computer vision methods and a GPS real time location

system for position estimation of excavators at construction sites. The vision data was collected from two surveillance cameras at the construction site and a GPS tracker was attached to the excavator for real-time location data, further the integrated system increased the accuracy of the system and reduced the computational work (Soltani et al., 2018).

Computer vision has also been demonstrated to offer the capability of automatically detecting unsafe behaviors and conditions on construction sites (Fang et al., 2020). According to Fang et al. (2019), computer vision allows for real-time detection of fall from heights and unsafe behavior at construction sites. In their study, computer vision was applied to automatically identify construction workers who moved on structural support without proper safety gear. In other research, computer vision has been utilized to identify individuals not wearing protective hard hats on construction sites (Fang et al., 2018). Kim et al. (2017) used computer vision for real time hazard identification of struck-by accidents between workers and heavy equipment on a construction site. The system used images captured from onsite cameras, and the workers were presented with visualized safety information using augmented reality (AR). Similarly, Son et al. (2019) used CV for real time hazard identification of collision accidents between workers and heavy equipment on construction sites using cameras equipped on the heavy equipment to detect possible collisions by estimating workers' positions. Notably, none of the mentioned researcher work reflects on the integrity of the construction workers in relation to the data capturing, method of analysis, and on the use of the results.

In table 1, some aspects of the different technologies are summarized.

Table 1 Some advantages and disadvantages of UWB, BLE, RFID, GPS, IMU and Computer vision

Technology	Advantages	Disadvantages	References
UWB	High accuracy	High cost	Siddiqui et al. (2019), Li et al. (2020)
BLE	Low cost, short response time, high scalability, low power consumption	Inferior connection stability and precision compared to UWB	Huang et al. (2021), Li et al. (2020)
RFID	Low cost	Limited range, affected by the arrangement of transmitters	Teizer (2015), Chae & Yoshida (2010), Montaser & Moselhi (2014), Li et al. (2020)
GPS	Suitable for outdoor positioning	Less accurate in indoor environments,	Li et al. (2020), Zhang et al. (2017)

		expensive for high accuracy	
IMU	Low cost, high availability, high scalability -> good positioning technology in combination with other methods	Less reliable technology for sole use due to the accumulation of positioning errors over time	Li et al., 2020
Computer vision	Promising for detecting hazards, identifying unsafe behavior, and preventing collisions	Camera view can be blocked by objects	Kim et al. (2017), Fang et al. (2019), Son et al. (2019)

A summary of identified safety technologies is listed in **Fel! Hittar inte referenskölla..**

2.4 Integrity, privacy and perception

With the massive amounts of data generated from sensors, internet connected devices, monitoring solutions and IoT systems privacy and data protection becomes a major concern. The technological developments have given employers increased opportunities to monitor their employees (SOU 2016:41). The implementation of technology for safety management involves collecting personal data (Oesterreich & Teuteberg, 2016), which raises ethical and legal concerns regarding the tracking and monitoring of employees and the handling of data. Monitoring of employees put high demands on the employer regarding personal integrity, and monitoring employees in the workplace must at all times be done with respect of the integrity and privacy of the workers.

While GDPR places a strong emphasis on consent as a lawful basis for the processing of personal data, such as images of one's face, this is not possible in a work setting due to the contractual relationship between employee and employer. This that the former cannot freely consent to the processing of information. For safety reasons, point 1d of article 6 of GDPR is much more likely to apply, namely, that the processing of data protects the vital interests of the data subject. This means that technology deployed for safety should be shown to be essential for protecting a worker's life or their physical or mental integrity.

As of May 2018, all organizations within the European Union are obliged to follow the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which regulates the protection of personal data, and it is the toughest privacy and security law in the world (European Commission, 2018). Personal data includes name, social security number, health data, biometric data, location information etc. Personal data at construction sites can be

collected by using camera surveillance, wearable sensors or tracking technology or some other technology. GDPR regulates how this data is collected and handled, and organizations must ensure that the data is well protected by implementing data protection strategies by design (European Commission, 2018).

In Sweden, there is no uniform legislation regarding personal integrity in working life. In May 2021, The Swedish Confederation of Professional Employees (TCO) demanded that the government appoint an inquiry to introduce a law protecting employee integrity in the workplace (Svanström, 2021). According to Donovan (n.d.) camera surveillance, real-time monitoring, monitoring clock in and out of work, performance measurements, positioning, and biometric data can be an invasion of personal integrity in working life. Private employers in Sweden who want to use positioning systems that can be linked to individual employees must normally be able to rely on a balance of interests, where, however, safety reasons outweigh efficiency reasons (Swedish Authority for Privacy Protection, 2021). According to JRC (2019) it is important to find a balance between protecting the privacy of individuals and allowing for innovation. IoT and other technologies have the potential to collect a lot of useful information, but if there are too strict limitations on data collection this may significantly limit the full potential of these systems (JRC, 2019).

Workers' acceptance of the technology is closely related to the success of implementation (Jacobs et al., 2019). The decision to implement a specific technology within an organization is, most often, led by upper management. But the use of the technology that allows one to take advantage of the expected benefits depends on the adoption of those who will use the technology (Talukder, 2012). According to Talukder (2012) there is a tendency for people to resist change if people are not certain of the direct benefits from it. By understanding the factors that can affect people's intentions to use technology, managers can develop strategies to increase and improve the adoption of technologies and make the innovation adoption process more effective (Sargent et al., 2012).

The acceptance of new technologies by workers depends on various factors such as organizational policies, their awareness of new technologies, training, socio-cultural differences, language barriers, etc. In addition to these factors, one of the most fundamental factors in workers' acceptance of new technology is the extent to which their privacy concerns are addressed. While companies use these technologies to increase security, productivity, and efficiency, it is important that they respect the privacy of their employees and protect their personal data.

At times, workers may feel compelled to accept the use of these technologies due to fear of job loss, which can influence their level of acceptance. As outlined in D6.5, when employees perceive that their data is being recorded and constantly monitored, they may fear that these records could be used against them in situations such as dismissals, thereby damaging the trust relationship with their employer. This fear can deter them from embracing technological solutions. Another restraint is the psychological discomfort caused by the sensation of constant surveillance. Construction workers, that were interviewed by ASHVIN partners in Spain and Sweden, believe that these technologies are intrusive, disrupt the harmony of the workplace, and paradoxically, could negatively impact their productivity. Consequently, the

inability to properly address confidentiality concerns can erode workers' trust in their employer, create a sense of psychological pressure, and affect their work commitment and quality.

In summary, there should be a balance between the utility of these technologies and the privacy of the workers. Here, this balance must be established by ensuring their privacy. Therefore, in such a trade-off between privacy and benefits, technology acceptance can serve as a protective nature for workers if the perceived benefits of these technologies outweigh their perceived risks (Schomakers, et.al., 2022). Thus, effectively addressing privacy concerns plays a key role in encouraging the adoption and correct use of the technologies implemented by employers. Consequently, it is crucial to undertake certain measures such as refraining from data collection unless necessary, anonymizing the collected data, restricting access to particularly sensitive data to authorized persons, ensuring that workers maintain control over their own data, and adhering to regulations and standards.

Individual factors and internal beliefs play a major role in deciding whether to adopt an innovation or not; these factors can be influenced by the organization and the social environment (Talukder, 2012). The culture and policies of an organization can encourage employees to try out and adopt new innovations. This could involve providing support and resources for employees to learn about and experiment with the innovation, as well as recognizing and rewarding employees who successfully implement it. By creating a positive environment for innovation, organizations can motivate their employees to act on the opportunity and put in the effort needed to adopt new technologies and ideas (Talukder, 2012). According to Bohrani (2016) top management support improves the overall technology adoption in an organization. Social factors, including colleagues and people in their social circles, are vital in safety technology deployment in the construction industry, as they can act as both drivers and barriers for the adoption of safety technology by workers (Bohrani, 2016). These factors can have both positive and negative effects on the adoption of technology. If employees observe people within their social group using a particular innovation, they are likely to be more inclined to adopt it as well. In some cases, employees may adopt an innovation not because they perceive it will be useful, but because they experience pressure from others to do so (Talukder, 2012). A similar change can be observed after the event of a serious or fatal accident, as workers then change their perception towards risks and technology adoption increases.

Other studies have identified additional factors affecting the acceptance of innovations among users in the construction sector. Son et al. (2012) found that user satisfaction is strongly linked to the success of implementation and the intent to use mobile computing devices by construction professionals. They conclude that social network, job relevance and support from top management, and training of technologies have a positive impact on the perceived ease of use, which in turn will have a positive impact on perceived usefulness and user satisfaction. Choi et al. (2017) found that the perceived usefulness, social influence, and perceived privacy risk are linked to construction workers intention to use wearables devices for safety purposes. According to Jacobs et al. (2019) implementing the technology for safety purposes has a much greater acceptance among employees compared to if the purpose is

monitoring for activity or productivity purposes. Choi et al. (2017) conclude that training sessions at the construction site where workers learn how the technology works and the safety benefits the technology can provide by experiencing it in an actual construction environment can have a positive impact on workers perceived usefulness. Furthermore, prior to implementing such technologies, management must pay attention to any potential privacy concerns the workers may experience (Choi et al., 2017). Lu and Deng (2022) investigated construction practitioners' use intention of an intelligent surveillance system and found that job relevance had a positive effect on perceived usefulness showing that if the technology was relevant to the construction professionals work resulted in a greater acceptance towards the technology. Further, supported by previous research they found that privacy risk had a negative impact on the intention to use the technology.

The factors highlighted above show that a consent-based approach to privacy, such as the one described in GDPR, may be sufficient to ensure legal protections, but does not guarantee the adoption of technology. To foster acceptance of technology and increase its effectiveness, developers should advocate for the contextual integrity of information flows (Nissebaum, 2004). In practical terms, this implies that the flows of information in construction should be transparent and explicit, i.e., who has access to which information, under what conditions, and for what purpose. This can be facilitated, for instance, by enabling workers to access and monitor the information collected about them. In a work setting, voluntary consent is unfeasible due to the power dynamics between employees and employers. Therefore, an approach based on contextual integrity, such as the one elaborated further in 6.5, is the most suitable method to respect and safeguard workers' rights to privacy.

2.5 Cyber-physical models and construction site safety

In the Ashvin context, the main concept in the Construction 4.0¹ approach is the CPS, the Cyber-physical system, see Figure 1. An online digital twin would be a typical example of a CPS. In the context of smart safety work, the CPS would, for example, facilitate warnings.

¹ Construction 4.0 refers to the application of Industry 4.0 practices to the construction industry. It involves the use of digital and smart technologies to connect all aspects of a building, making work more efficient and effective. This digital transformation includes digitalized design, construction, and operation.

The concept of Construction 4.0 is gradually affecting the construction industry, which has traditionally lagged behind other sectors in adopting technological advances. The complex nature of the construction industry and its heavy reliance on information necessitate the adoption of these new and emerging technologies.

Figure 1 Conceptual model of a cyber-physical system (CPS) (Adapted from Sawhney et al., 2020)

In a typical scenario, a sensor might detect the absence of fall protection on a floor slab, thereby creating a risk of falling from one floor to the lower floor. This data would then be transmitted to the cyber model. Upon receiving the data, either a human or an AI algorithm would determine that the situation needs to be rectified. Consequently, an action would be triggered, issuing a ticket to the on-site colleagues to install the protective component. This process could be activated every few hours, ensuring continuous monitoring and prompt response. If it is active in real time, more opportunities can be revealed. A sensor mounted on a crane could automatically geolocate an ongoing heavy lift, transmitting the data to a cyber model. Simultaneously, a safety zone could be established within this model. In the meantime, a sensor attached to a worker's helmet, who is moving in the vicinity, is also geolocated, and its location data is relayed to the cyber model. If an AI algorithm determines that the worker is on a trajectory to enter the designated safety zone, it can trigger, for example, an alarm within the helmet. This preemptive measure effectively prevents the worker from inadvertently moving beneath the heavy load.

Rudberg and Sezer (2021) reported on a collaboration between NCC, Scharc, and Linköping University where this approach has been tried. The partners tested Bluetooth beacons, a web-based collaboration application built around the IFC model, the digital twin concept, and IoT sensor technologies for fall and hit detection, localization, and danger zones. The site management found these technologies, especially the danger zones, to be useful. They also found these technologies to be beneficial in planning for increased site productivity.

This work was continued in a collaboration project involving NCC, Microsoft, ARROW, Sigma, Edins Byggkranar, and Linköping University (Sezer and Rudberg, 2022). Cameras were mounted on the boom of the tower crane, capturing images that were processed in a computer located in the crane cab. The computer identified the positions of people, vehicles, and the crane hook. A defined area, "Safe under the construction crane", was established under the boom to determine whether people were within an alarm area. If any people or vehicles were detected in this zone, the crane operator was immediately alerted, see Figure 2. It is important to emphasize that no individual could be linked to the collected material to ensure personal privacy.

Figure 2 Identifying possible hazard situations and giving the crane driver more insights (Photo: NCC)

Based on five similar case studies, Rudberg and Sezer (2022) summarized the use of digital technologies for improving site safety. The paper focused on three areas: the technical feasibility, user acceptance, and the possibility to scale-up and commercialise the digital technologies. It showed that that “the construction context puts extra demand on development when it comes to technical feasibility, whereas the user acceptance is generally good. The main challenge is, however, to show commercial benefits and scale-up the technology for broader implementation in the industry”.

2.6 Cyber-physical models in the design phase to increase construction site safety

Virtual Reality (VR) technologies currently in use are built upon concepts originating from the 1960s and earlier. Ivan Sutherland's pioneering work in 1968 (Sutherland, 1968) introduced the first head-mounted display capable of rendering basic wireframe models to match the viewer's changing posture. This innovative invention established the groundwork for the technologies known today as Virtual Reality (VR), Augmented Reality (AR), and Mixed Reality (MR), as outlined by Milgram et al. (1995) in their reality-virtuality continuum. This continuum represents a continuous spectrum spanning from entirely virtual to entirely real experiences. VR is commonly defined as computer-generated environments or realities crafted to closely simulate a person's physical presence within a captivating and immersive setting. The primary objective of VR is to enable individuals to perceive and interact with the virtual environment in a manner indistinguishable from the physical world. The first applications were found in the areas of gaming, marketing, and advertising but has in the last decade moved into the construction sector whereas identifying clash detections already in the design phase is a typical successful use-case. Also in the construction phase, VR has been used to achieve an understanding of dimensions, scales and buildability aspects that are otherwise difficult to realize with 2D drawings or even 3D BIM models (Johansson and Roupé (2022)).

In the construction industry, ensuring safety at the construction site has traditionally been the responsibility of the contractor. This responsibility arises from the constructor's authority over construction workers, project schedule, work methods, their sequence, and the contractual relationships among project team members. However, architects and engineers involved in designing the project can also contribute to enhancing site safety. The rationale behind their involvement is based on the principle of occupational safety and health, which states that the most effective way to safeguard workers is by eliminating safety hazards from the work site. Designing with the goal of eliminating hazards has been proven to be more effective than merely controlling or protecting workers from those hazards (Manuele, 2013). However, designing for safety relies on the integration of construction process knowledge and the incorporation of proven methods into the design. Many architects and engineers are not prepared to address this deficiency and lack proper training and understanding. Although the use of VR in design processes has primarily been limited to serving as a complementary reviewing tool alongside other information media like 2D drawings and 3D models, VR is increasingly recognized as a potential solution for enhancing understanding of the safety implications of design solutions. This will be further elaborated in Chapter 4.4.

3 ASHVIN HEALTH & SAFETY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM

The construction site is a dynamic and constantly changing workplace, with various tasks being performed simultaneously each day. This introduces new risk factors or hazards at unknown times and places, leading to dangers arising due to these conditions. Workers, safety supervisors, managers, and team leaders must constantly manage these different risks that arise and monitor potential risk factors.

Despite the importance of hazard identification and risk awareness, studies have demonstrated that a significant proportion of hazards remain unrecognized, exposing workers to workplace dangers (Alex et al., 2014, Almaskati et al., 2024). Site personnel must rely on previous experience and skills to handle both identified and unidentified hazards and adapt their behavior accordingly. Their ability in dangerous situations is influenced by both human and contextual factors, such as their awareness of safety, motivation, time pressure, peer pressure, etc. This means that the site personnel's ability to detect hazards varies greatly depending on where they are and whether something or someone around them poses a danger to their safety.

Presently, effective communication is emphasized as a critical factor in preventing accidents at construction sites (Helen et al., 2019). Real-time communication technology for work teams is an effective method to reduce accident risk factors significantly. Further, accidents tend to happen when workers are subjected to unforeseen risks and lack focus or awareness at the same time, therefore utilizing technology to detect hazards and immediately warning workers can empower them to change their actions and prevent serious accidents.

In addition, an organization's strict safety management can regulate unsafe workplace behaviors and conditions. Safety management is key to reducing human-related risks, which can be tackled through training and appropriate use of safety devices and inspections. Traditional safety management is about ensuring that workers are informed of risks associated with work activities beforehand. Introducing digital technologies on sites allow new possibilities to increase health and safety. Thus, an ASHVIN framework for health and safety on construction sites, complementing traditional frameworks, is proposed, see Figure 3. This framework takes the advantage of the digital technologies and tools investigated and developed in the other tasks in the Ashvin project, contextualized for safety.

Figure 3 ASHVIN framework on health and safety on the construction sites

The framework, with a user-centric approach, consists of four elements:

- Safety training,
- Image-based risk detection technology,
- Sensor-based detection technology, and
- On-site risk change assessment technology.

To each of these elements, we will in the following chapters illustrate cases based on the ASHVIN scope and activities.

4 SAFETY TRAINING AND PRACTICAL CASES

The importance of construction site safety, as pointed out in the previous chapters, sets the stage for the following chapter. Here, we delve deeper into training for construction safety, AI, and digital twins, exploring how these technologies can be utilized to create and update training programs. We begin with a general introduction on the development of targeted training programs. Subsequently, we explore the theory of enhancing construction site safety training with AI, sensors, and digital twins.

In Section 4.3, we shift our focus to the practical applicability of using AI for training. For instance, we discuss how e-learning modules can be created using generative AI and provide an example of what an e-learning prototype might look like. We present a practical case study involving data collection and detail the process involved. Finally, in section 4.4, we illustrate how VR can be employed to heighten safety awareness during the design and planning phase.

4.1 Developing Targeted Training Programs for Construction Site Safety

In the construction industry, ensuring the safety of workers and minimizing the risks associated with construction sites is of paramount importance. One key approach to achieving this is through the development of targeted training programs that are specifically designed to address the unique needs and challenges of construction site safety. In this chapter, we will explore the general process of creating effective training programs for construction site safety, including the key principles and considerations involved. Figure 4 shows a flow chart diagram of the five proposed steps.

Figure 4 Process for designing targeted training programs for construction site safety

Step 1: Needs Assessment

The first step in designing a targeted training program for construction site safety is conducting a comprehensive needs assessment. This involves identifying the specific safety needs and challenges faced by workers on construction sites, as well as any barriers or constraints that may affect the effectiveness of the training program. This can be done through methods such as site inspections, incident reports, worker surveys, and interviews to gather data on factors such as common hazards, safety regulations, equipment operation, emergency response, and worker knowledge and skills. The needs assessment provides a solid foundation for tailoring the training program to the unique requirements of construction site safety.

Step 2: Setting SMART Goals

Once the needs assessment is completed, the next step is to set Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound (SMART) goals for the training program. SMART goals provide a clear and measurable framework for evaluating the effectiveness of the training program in improving construction site safety. For example, a SMART goal could be to reduce the number of fall-related incidents on the construction site by 25% within six months through the implementation of a comprehensive fall prevention training program. Setting realistic and achievable goals ensures that the training program is designed to address the identified safety needs and objectives of the construction site.

Step 3: Designing the Training Program

Based on the needs assessment and SMART goals, the training program is designed to meet the specific safety requirements of the construction site. This includes determining the appropriate training methods, content, format, and delivery mechanisms for the program. The training program should cover topics such as hazard recognition, equipment operation, emergency response, safety regulations, and best practices for construction site safety. It should also incorporate interactive and participatory elements, such as simulations, case studies, and hands-on activities, to engage learners and facilitate effective learning. The training program should be tailored to the diverse workforce in the construction industry, considering factors such as language, literacy, and cultural differences. Incorporating best practice examples in learning principles and construction site safety guidelines ensure that the training program is grounded in scientific principles.

Step 4: Implementation and Monitoring

Once the training program is designed, it is implemented on the construction site. This involves delivering the program in a structured and organized manner, ensuring that all workers receive the necessary training and resources to understand and apply the safety practices. The training program should be supplemented with ongoing monitoring to assess its effectiveness in meeting the SMART goals and to identify any areas that may require adjustments. Monitoring may include safety observations, incident reports, worker feedback, and assessments of knowledge and skills. Regular reviews and evaluations of the training program are conducted to ensure that it remains relevant and effective in addressing the safety needs of the construction site.

Step 5: Evaluation and Continuous Improvement

The final step in the process of creating targeted training programs for construction site safety is evaluating the overall effectiveness of the program and making continuous improvements based on the data and feedback collected during the implementation and monitoring phases. Evaluation involves analyzing the safety outcomes and results of the training program in relation to the SMART goals and the identified safety needs of the construction site. This may involve data analysis, statistical assessments, and comparison to established safety benchmarks or standards. Based on the evaluation findings, adjustments can be made to the training program, such as updating content, and revising delivery.

4.2 Enhancing Construction Site Safety Training with AI and Digital Twins

The construction industry has seen significant advancements in technology, including the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI), and digital twins (Chacón et al., 2024). The same technologies have also the potential to revolutionize the way construction site safety training is conducted. These technologies offer new opportunities to improve the effectiveness, efficiency, and safety of training programs by providing real-time data, analytics, and simulations that can enhance the learning experience and help workers develop critical safety skills. In this chapter, we will explore how AI and digital twins of buildings can be utilized to enhance the process of creating and delivering construction site safety training programs.

AI in Construction Site Safety Training

The use of AI can potentially transform the landscape of construction site safety training. By analyzing vast amounts of data, including site conditions, worker behaviors, and equipment usage, AI algorithms can pinpoint potential safety hazards and predict unsafe situations. This data-driven methodology aids in the creation of targeted, customized training programs that tackle specific safety risks and offer personalized feedback to workers. For instance, AI can analyze sensor data from wearable devices to monitor workers' movements, providing real-time feedback on body posture, lifting techniques, and ergonomics which encourages workers to cultivate safe work habits.

Furthermore, AI can also be used in virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) training simulations. These simulations have the capability to mirror real-world construction site scenarios, offering workers a safe and controlled environment to practice safety procedures. AI algorithms can evaluate the workers' performance in these simulations and provide feedback on their decision-making, hazard recognition, and emergency response capabilities, thereby aiding them in enhancing their safety skills.

Digital Twins of Buildings

Digital twins provide a detailed and dynamic representation of the building, capturing real-time data on its performance, maintenance needs, and safety features. This data can be utilized to develop interactive training programs that allow workers to virtually navigate through the building, identify potential safety hazards, and practice safety procedures in a realistic environment.

Digital twins can also facilitate remote training and collaboration, allowing workers to access training materials, simulations, and feedback from anywhere, at any time. This can be particularly beneficial for workers in remote or hazardous locations where on-site training may be challenging or risky.

4.3 Construction Site Safety e-learning based on AI insights

E-learning platforms (such as "Easygenerator", "Talent LMS" or "Moodle") can be combined with AI to automatically update the content. AI can be used to analyze and process data from various sources, such as construction site sensor data, and other relevant data, and generate insights or predictions that can be used to update the content in the eLearning platforms. For the e-learning creation, Generative AI, also

known as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) can be used. It is a type of artificial intelligence (AI) that involves the use of machine learning algorithms to generate new data that is similar to the input data it was trained on. GANs consist of two neural networks, a generator and a discriminator, that are trained together in a process called adversarial training.²

For example, if the AI model detects patterns of safety incidents or near-misses from sensor data, it can automatically trigger updates in the eLearning platform to incorporate the latest safety guidelines or best practices. The AI model can also analyze worker performance data and provide personalized recommendations for additional training modules or resources to address specific skill gaps or areas of improvement.

Additionally, AI can be used to analyze data from user interactions with the eLearning platform, such as learner engagement, assessment scores, and feedback, to automatically adapt and personalize the content based on individual learner needs. This can help ensure that the training content remains relevant, up-to-date, and aligned with the evolving needs of the construction industry.

Integration of AI with eLearning platforms can be achieved through APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) or other integration methods provided by the eLearning platforms or the AI tools used. This may require customization or development work to connect the AI model with the eLearning platform, depending on the specific requirements and capabilities of the platforms involved.

It is worth noting that the integration of AI with eLearning platforms should be done carefully, considering factors such as data privacy, security, and ethical considerations. Proper data handling and compliance with applicable laws and regulations, such as data protection regulations, should be ensured to protect the privacy and rights of the learners and other stakeholders involved.

For the purpose of Ashvin, an example of an onboarding and e-learning for a construction site was developed. A platform gives the user the possibility to sign up to the construction site, get a general e-learning and AI-based safety advice (this example is a Figma mock-up of the ASHVIN Kineum Demo Case³). It is visible that the platform supports the onboarding process from an administrative perspective, but also helps with basic information about the construction site. Requirements regarding barriers and safety equipment are given, and lastly current information.

² The generator in a GAN learns to generate realistic data samples, such as images, audio, or text, by generating data from random input noise. The discriminator, on the other hand, learns to distinguish between real data samples from the training set and fake data samples generated by the generator. The generator and discriminator are trained iteratively in a process where the generator tries to generate data that can fool the discriminator, and the discriminator tries to correctly classify whether the data is real or fake.

³ <https://www.figma.com/proto/5qVcSfRnczorfO5BWzNxq/Plan-B-mockups?page-id=473%3A2&node-id=500-34&viewport=-75%2C322%2C0.3&scaling=min-zoom&starting-point-node-id=473%3A4>

Figure 5 Screenshots of an onboarding and safety information platform prototype for the Kineum building (Ashvin Demo Case)

Furthermore, an e-learning prototype for the Kineum building was developed, based on Talent LMS. This prototype was created manually, but could be integrated with AI through an API, as described above

(<https://planb.talentlms.com/shared/start/key:LEEIDNHR>).

The e-learning prototype also includes a quiz to ensure the relevant information was understood by the user. In the Figure 6 below, aspects of the quiz are shown, asking about safety equipment and barrier requirements.

Figure 6 Screenshots of the quiz of an onboarding and safety information e-learning prototype for the Kineum building (Ashvin Demo Case) based on Talent LMS

A third practical way of using AI generated trainings is video and chat advice. Platforms like D-ID Studio⁴ generate instruction and explanatory videos and chat-bots which help with trainings and questions a user might have around the training or the content of the training, such as necessary safety equipment (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Screenshot of an AI generated chat-bot video to showcase the use around questions of the training content

⁴ This is one example; more and more video AI-based video generators are becoming available and accessible.

4.4 Introducing safety awareness in the design and planning phase

With the advances indicated in section 2.5 in mind, it was decided to carry out a study to examine if collaborative VR could support the structural engineers to design solutions that incorporated safe assembly on the construction site. The ASHVIN demonstration site Kineum was used as an example.

To test the hypothesis, a workshop was conducted with a small group of construction professionals and academicians. Because the foci of research, a workshop offers valuable opportunities for researchers to explore specialized subjects by engaging with a small group of participants, resulting in detailed and unique data that surveys or interviews may not capture (Ahmed and Asraf, 2018). Furthermore, it was also expected that a workshop could facilitate a collaborative environment where participants can exchange their experiences and insights, which was one of our main purposes.

The workshop included a paper 2D plan exercise and a multi-user VR walk-through within a virtual site scenario resembling construction processes for hazard identification and discussion of hazard preventive safety measures. To develop scenarios for the walk through via VR, a BIM model of the Kineum project was used.

To develop a proper workshop agenda and formulate questions for the participants, several meetings and discussions were conducted with structural engineers, a safety engineer, and a lead VDC (Virtual Design and Construction) developer of NCC. Furthermore, relevant information and data was collected from NCC's safety documents and H&S database. To simulate the VR scenarios, the BIM model of the Kineum building and relevant BIM components were imported to the software BIMXplorer V1.7.5⁵. Utilizing the interface of a touchscreen board, the BIM components were set up in the BIM model and various site scenarios were simulated.

4.4.1 Three site scenarios

The plan of sixth floor of Kineum building was chosen for our cases study, using the features and options of BIMXplorer and the BIM objects/components to adjust the BIM model. Through this procedure, three construction site scenarios for the VR simulations were developed, Figure 8.

Figure 8 Three scenarios developed for the VR part of the workshop

⁵ BIMXplorer (<https://www.bimxplorer.com/>) is provided by Chalmers University of Technology. BIMXplorer is a fast and easy-to-use real-time viewer specifically designed to handle large and complex Building Information Models (BIM). It works as a plugin to Autodesk Revit as well as a standalone application that can import IFC files (Industry Foundation Classes).

- **Scenario 1- The unsafe scenario:**

The unsafe scenario involves a specific time period characterized by the start of construction planning after the completion of structural work. During this phase, the structural aspects of the project are almost finished, and there are no walls, windows, doors, furnishings, MEP components, or finishing works. To create this scenario, certain objects in the 3D model were intentionally hidden. This was achieved by filtering approximately 72 elements based on their descriptions, type name, object class, and schedule code using BIMXplorer 1.7.5 (Figure 9). Additionally, to make the site more unsafe in terms of openings, no safety precaution components were set in the model, and additional objects were placed on the sixth floor, increasing the potential hazards.

Figure 9 Filtering set: hiding architecture file in BIMXplorer.

- **Scenario 2 – Scenario with different subcontractors’ materials imitating the 2D site layout plan**

The simulation for this scenario was done imitating a 2D site layout plan of the sixth floor of Kineum Project as of May 2021. The 2D site layout plan of the sixth floor depicts the areas of different subcontractors such as painters, ventilation, electricity etc. In the BIM model, the BIM components such as painting equipment, ventilation equipment, and electrical equipment were set up in the same area to create the simulated site scenario.

Figure 10 Preparation of site scenario of Kineum floor 6 following the 2D site layout plan of the 6th floor of Kineum Project (May 2021) in BIMXplorer with the help of a touchscreen board

- **Scenario 3 – Safe scenario**

The same unsafe scenario with filters was used to plan a safer construction site on the sixth floor of the Kineum building. As the focus in terms of safety is on openings, safety precautions from different tools for openings are applied to the model. These safety objects were prepared and saved in advance. Loading prefab folders, saving, opening, and adding the prefab files were the main actions in that step as well.

Following the recommendations of the Construction Industry Institute (CII)⁶, permanent guardrails were applied around floor openings in concrete slabs, particularly those situated in high-traffic passageways, see Figure 11. To prevent tripping hazards, the recommendations advise to keep steps, curbs, and slab depressions away from window openings, exterior edges, and floor openings. In this scenario, there was a triangular opening that was connected to both a stair and a ramp. This opening was also situated near a window. To ensure safety, a permanent guardrail was installed near this opening. In this scenario, there was a triangular opening that was connected to both a stair and a ramp. This opening was situated near a window. To ensure safety, a permanent guardrail was installed near this opening.

⁶ www.construction-institute.org

Figure 11 Screenshots of all the safer opening groups presented in BIMXplorer and they are numbered in the 2D plan view of floor 6 of Kineum Project

4.4.2 Workshop

The topic of the workshop was collaborative safety planning through comparison between 2D and VR. The purpose of the workshop was to discuss how to improve the safety of construction workers already at the design phase supported by VR. Furthermore, the aim was also to investigate if VR can improve collaboration regarding safety planning of construction sites and aid the construction team to be better prepared. The nine workshop participants represented a diverse range of professions related to industrial research and development, structural engineering, virtual design and construction, construction safety, and academia.

The feedback and reflections differed according to the participants' backgrounds and experiences. However, collectively they were representing the different perspectives necessary to achieve a productive and efficient outcome for the site planning.

Results of the exercise with a 2D plan

The participants were provided with printed copies of the 2D plan of floor 6 of the Kineum building, see Figure 12. The participants were then asked to identify some areas in the 2D drawings, which, according to their opinion, can be hazardous during construction period. Since the literature review suggested fall hazards to be the most common types of accidents prevalent in the construction industry, this exercise aimed to determine how many potentially hazardous areas, particularly openings, can be identified from a conventional 2D plan view for safety planning.

Figure 12 2D plan view of the sixth floor of the Kineum building

During the exercise, each participant marked and identified different openings as hazardous areas. Based on the participants' activities during the 2D exercise, it could be observed that most of them were able to identify common openings, such as elevator shafts and stairwell openings, in a 2D plan view drawing (see Figure 13a). However, identifying unique openings specific to a project solely through a 2D drawing can be challenging. For instance, during the exercise, the triangular opening near the terrace on the sixth floor plan was a distinctive feature that went unnoticed by the majority of participants (see Figure 13b). These findings highlight the limitations of relying solely on a 2D plan view drawing to effectively identify hazardous areas like openings. Consequently, it is difficult to adequately consider and plan safety precautions based solely on a 2D layout, similar to the challenge of pinpointing hazardous areas accurately.

(a) (b)

Figure 13 (a) All openings marked in the 2D plan view of floor 6 of Kineum Project; (b) The triangular opening near the terrace that was not recognized by most participants during the exercise.

Results of the Virtual reality exercise

In the subsequent step of the workshop, further progress was made in the hazard identification process, utilizing the capabilities of VR. To further explore these safety issues, the workshop employed multi-user VR technology to show an unsafe scenario with no safety precautions in place. Participants navigated through the BIM project using multi-user VR and focused on the same safety issues as in the 2D drawing exercise. Participants were instructed to engage in virtual walkthroughs of the sixth floor area of the Kineum project, paying particular attention to the area around the opening, in order to identify potential hazards using VR technology. Subsequently, they were tasked with drawing safety objects in the identified area through a collaborative discussion rather than individually.

Scenario 1 – Unsafe scenario

Each participant successfully completed the VR walkthrough and identified nearly all the openings on the sixth floor of Kineum building in VR, individually. They utilized the marking tool to sketch guardrails (see Figure 14). By leveraging the fly mode functionality within VR, participants can fly to the exact direction and closely examine the details of components and projects. During the utilization of virtual reality (VR) for hazard identification, one structural engineer participant examined the column's specifications to verify its accurate installation. Another participant, whose background is in architectural engineering, utilized the fly mode to move outside the building and conduct an in-depth review of the facade's details.

After performing hazard identification in VR, a VDC expert realized that the selected case project was a simple example. However, the expert also noted that there could be construction sites with more complex situations. For instance, VR can be particularly beneficial in providing a comprehensive awareness of risks and preventive measures, especially in situations where buildings are situated in close proximity to one another. During the VR activities, individuals or pairs engaged in immersive experiences, while the rest of the participants gathered around a touchscreen board. The board displayed the BIM model in BIMXplorer, enabling collaborative discussions on secure site planning. The touchscreen board was integrated into the VR headset to present the instant progress in the BIMX project.

Besides the construction solutions of the details of the building, different impacts on construction site safety were also discussed. One of the attendees suggested enhancing safety measures by incorporating sensors to monitor different aspects of the construction site, such as temperature, humidity, noise levels, dust levels, emergency exits, and warnings. By utilizing virtual reality (VR) technology, these sensors can provide real-time data on several factors that impact safety.

Figure 14 Screenshots of sketched guardrails in several opening by participants in VR.

Scenario 2 - Results of site layout plan discussion

From the conversations during the VR walk through for site layout plan discussion, it can be inferred that VR site layout plan can help designers in preparing a more efficient site layout plan. While in 2D site layout plan only the areas designated to subcontractors are visible, in the simulated VR site layout plan different materials and components can be viewed in a real scale. By realizing the spatial context in detailed and 1:1 scale, simulated site scenario can support the designers in comprehending the purpose of the slab for material storage during construction process. This intuitive understanding of the scale and spatial relationships between different building components and materials can aid in identifying and marking the slab load capacity more accurately than compared to 2D site layout plan.

Together with safety engineers, the VR walk through discussion in the simulated model in the design and planning phase can not only raise awareness of the designers but also support them in contributing to a better safety plan and strategy. This type of collaboration discussion between design and safety team utilizing the VR can aid in transferring and exchanging knowledge and information between the design and construction phase and can reduce miscommunication. By ensuring better information flow, the construction team would be better prepared and overall safety would be increased.

Figure 15 Two participants wearing VR headsets and others joining through the touchscreen board and the projector screen during the VR exercise

Scenario 3 - Safe scenario

In this phase of the workshop, a multi-user VR system was utilized to showcase an alternative safe site scenario for the sixth floor of the Kineum building. The scenario integrated suggestions from various tools and regulations to ensure safety. The main goal was to provide engineers with a comprehensive understanding of this alternative scenario, demonstrating the identification and resolution of safety concerns. This presentation served as a training session aimed at enhancing engineers' awareness of safety issues. By raising their awareness and educating them on the practical implementation of safety measures, engineers can be empowered to proactively identify and mitigate potential hazards in their future projects.

The multi-user VR presentation encouraged active participation and engagement from the participants, and provided them with opportunities for discussion, questions, and feedback (Figure 15). During the VR session, the participants realized that the simulated environment they were in, referred to as the "safe site scenario", was safer compared to the "unsafe scenario" designed for the VR exercise (Figure 16).

Figure 16 Multi-user VR meeting on discussion about safe site solutions (Different users are visible with different colors of avatars).

The participants introduced additional precautions specifically for the elevator shaft in the proposed safe scenario, which the researchers classified as light safety measures (Figure 17). One of the structural engineers also noted that he/she could identify openings in the layout and incorporate commonly used safety objects. However, it was not possible to accurately select the appropriate safety objects and guardrails based on their specific features. Regarding collaborative design, the safety engineer replied that no collaborative work had been conducted thus far in previous projects, and the interactions with the structural engineering teams were limited to site planning discussions. One of the structural engineers mentioned that they solely focused on individual designs for site planning. The safety engineer highlighted an additional challenge that necessitates collaboration with structural engineers: when the decision is made to install guardrails, such as those around the floor perimeter, it becomes crucial to involve designers in determining the suitable structural solution for their respective designs.

Figure 17 Overlapping view of safety planning in VR with the proposed safe scenario

Furthermore, a noteworthy aspect is the utilization of temporary plywood covers in an area designated for material lifting. As an enhancement to the designed safe site alternative, the safety engineer explained that they employed plywood to seal off the elevator shaft openings, creating platforms for construction workers to perform their tasks in that specific area.

4.4.3 Reflections on the workshop session

Near the end of the discussions and activities, the participants were asked to answer some questions according to their opinion of the workshop sessions. This final part of the workshop aimed to gather all participants' reflections on the activities with yes/no questions and some optional comments that motivate their answers. In total, there were 19 questions, and the questions were divided into four parts. While the full results can be found in Huseynli and Tasnim (2023), Figure 18 summarizes the general conclusions of the workshop. As can be seen from the results, the large majority of the

participants acknowledged the support of the tools in achieving a better understanding of the site layout and its challenges regarding safety.

Figure 18 Summary of the general reflections of the workshop

5 IMAGE-BASED RISK DETECTION

The next component of the framework to be discussed is the image-based risk detection. Here, images are the main source of information. This is illustrated by a case study that has been carried out. In this testbed project, a camera at the entrance gate to a construction site to check that the personnel entering the site was wearing the mandatory safety gear – safety goggles, helmet with the chin strap attached and high visibility clothing (Rudberg, Henschel & Sezer, 2022).

The camera utilized computer vision and AI with deep learning capabilities for image recognition and object detection. The AI was trained in two models – first to detect if a human being was present in the image, and if so a second model was applied to detect the defined safety gear.

The data was used for two purposes:

- 1) direct feedback to the gate with either warnings about faulty equipment or even closing the gate, not allowing the person to enter.
- 2) aggregated data for overview and following the development over time.

As described in the project's white paper, the left part of the diagram presented below illustrates the process by which the solution retrieves images from the network camera that has been installed at the entrance gate. The images are analysed on a local computer on the local network ("IoT Edge") and the results can be presented directly to the person entering the construction site, see Figure 19.

Figure 19 General process view of the implemented model for the test project "Säker inpassering på bygget" (Secure entrance to the construction site)

Results from the model were sent to an Azure cloud for the purpose of training and refining the model. When the model was trained, data was sent back to the local network at the construction site. This process of iterative training, testing, and retraining was carried out continuously in order to improve the model's overall performance. In addition to the Azure cloud, information from the model was also sent to the cloud for analysis and visualization in Power BI. This enabled the monitoring of protective equipment use and offered both a current summary of the aggregated data, as well as a review of its evolution over time. The process is illustrated in Figure 20.

This aggregated data was used manually in the test project as material for discussions about safety, but it could also automatically feed a training program as described in section 4.1. Together with more data from a digital twin and other sensors on site the aggregated data would provide an automatic evaluation of the training program as well as the possibility to alter it for continuous improvement, thus fulfilling step 5 as described in section 4.1 "Evaluation and Continuous Improvement". This automation would optimize the agile and continuous evaluation and improvement of trainings based on the data and feedback collected during the implementation and monitoring phases.

It would also be possible to adjust the trainings based on current events and geolocation, and even generate new material with instant reaction. If for example a sensor detects harmful particles in a particular zone on one floor of a building, screens on site or notifications directly to workers close by could instantly inform about the situation and provide information about the proper safety equipment for the situation. This data driven approach of integrating sensors with a digital twin using a generative AI to provide workers with instant information and to increase construction site safety can be set up as an agile framework which can also produce customized and up to date training material. This approach can improve the effectiveness and efficiency of training programs, as well as enhance workplace safety.

Figure 20

Process for automatic identification of safety equipment (Image: NCC)

6 SENSOR-BASED RISK DETECTION

6.1 Data from construction-based sensors

Sensors play a crucial role in collecting real-time data from construction sites, which can be used to enhance construction site safety training. Sensors can be deployed in various locations on construction sites to capture data on environmental conditions, equipment usage, and worker activities. For example, sensors can monitor noise levels, temperature, humidity, and air quality, providing insights into potential health hazards for workers. Sensors can also track the usage of heavy equipment, such as cranes and excavators, and provide data on equipment performance, maintenance needs, and operator behavior.

Training AI to effectively analyze sensor data and predict safety hazards requires large amounts of labeled data. The data used to train AI algorithms for construction site safety can come from various sources. Some of the common sources of data include:

Historical Records: Data from past accidents, near-misses, safety incidents, and other safety-related incidents can be collected and used to train AI algorithms. This data can provide insights into the root causes of accidents and help identify patterns and trends that can be used to develop predictive models.

Sensor Data: Data collected from sensors on construction sites, such as environmental sensors, equipment sensors, and worker activity sensors, can be used to train AI algorithms. This data can include parameters such as temperature, humidity, noise levels, equipment performance, and worker behaviors.

Construction Site Data: Data collected from construction site operations, such as project schedules, material usage, and worker schedules, can also be used to train AI algorithms. This data can provide contextual information about the construction site and its operations, which can be used to improve the accuracy of safety predictions. The implementation of technology for safety management involves collecting personal data (Oesterreich & Teuteberg, 2016), which can be a data privacy issue (see also chapter 2.4).

Industry Standards and Regulations: Data from industry standards, regulations, and best practices related to construction site safety can also be used to train AI algorithms. This data can provide guidelines and benchmarks for safety performance, which can be incorporated into the AI models for safety prediction and accident prevention.

The format of the data used for training AI algorithms can vary depending on the type of data and the specific requirements of the AI model. It can include numerical data, categorical data, time-series data, and textual data. Data preprocessing techniques, such as data cleaning, normalization, and feature engineering, may be applied to prepare the data for training.

6.2 Training data for AI

The data can be used to train AI algorithms using machine learning techniques, such as supervised or unsupervised learning, to identify patterns, correlations, and anomalies in the data that are indicative of safety risks. As the AI algorithm continues to analyze sensor data and learn from new data inputs, it can improve its accuracy and predictive capabilities over time. It can adapt to changing site conditions, equipment usage, and worker behaviors, and provide more accurate and timely alerts for accident

prevention. Regular updates and retraining of the AI algorithm with new data can further enhance its performance and effectiveness in preventing accidents on construction sites.

AI algorithms can analyze the data collected from sensors to identify potential safety hazards and predict unsafe conditions. For example, AI can analyze noise data to detect high noise levels that may indicate a risk of hearing damage for workers. AI can analyze temperature and humidity data to identify potential heat stress risks for workers. AI can also analyze equipment performance data to detect anomalies that may indicate a potential equipment failure or malfunction.

Based on the analysis of sensor data, systems or applications can generate real-time alerts or notifications to workers, supervisors, or safety personnel, prompting them to take appropriate actions to prevent accidents. For instance, if noise levels exceed safe thresholds, the system can send alerts to workers to wear hearing protection. If temperature and humidity levels indicate a risk of heat stress, the system can send notifications to workers to take breaks and hydrate. If equipment performance data indicates a potential failure, this can trigger maintenance requests or shut down the equipment to prevent accidents.

6.3 Data fusion for improved site safety

Sensor data fusion builds upon these systems, offering a more sophisticated approach. As an illustration, sensor data from the demonstrator Kineum was used. All available environmental sensor data collected from multiple sensor units on each floor (typically two per floor) were combined to detect occupancy in multiple rooms. This approach was implemented to build a model that can accurately detect occupancy in each individual room. Environmental sensors were combined to detect occupancy in each one of the rooms.

A substantial collection of historical data, collected from the construction site, was used to train predictive models in a machine learning framework. This data-driven modeling approach involved dividing our comprehensive dataset into distinct subsets, specifically for training and testing the models. We adopted a conventional 80/20 split, where 80% of the data was used for model training, and the remaining 20% was utilized for testing. This methodology is widely recognized in the field of machine learning and is highly effective in preventing overfitting while still providing sufficient data for robust model training.

The training phase involved using the larger subset of data to instruct the model to recognize patterns and dependencies between the different variables. Once the model was adequately trained, it was subsequently tested on the remaining unseen data, effectively gauging its predictive capabilities and performance. By doing so, we were able to assess how well our model generalizes to new, unseen data – a crucial aspect of a model's predictive capacity.

The evaluation process spanned several models⁷, each with unique characteristics and potential benefits. We performed a rigorous set of experiments on the historical

⁷ The models evaluated included Support Vector Machines (SVM), Random Forests (RF), k-Nearest Neighbors (kNN), Gradient Boosting (GB), Gaussian Naive Bayes (GNB), and Decision Trees (DT).

data, comparing the predictive performance of each model. The empirical results revealed the superiority of an ensemble algorithm, namely LGBM (Light Gradient Boosting Machine)⁸. This algorithm displayed remarkable predictive capability and outperformed the other models in our specific application of occupancy detection. The results showed that occupancy detection can be achieved with high levels of accuracy (Figure 21 Occupancy Detection Process). A more detailed description of this process can be found in Deliverable 3.3. This tool is useful for the several stakeholders, each with different values. As an example, construction site crimes (such as vandalism, trespassing, or theft) are a major problem for the sector. In a study in Sweden 2022, 57 percent of construction company owners reported that they were subjected to crimes during the past year. This tool can detect unwanted presence in a space, which may prevent or notify the site management of possible criminal activities, without violating privacy issues. Another potential use case regards health and safety. Presence outside approved work hours can indicate injured personnel and the site manager can then quickly act. This tool, called SMT (Safety Management Tool), was developed by CERTH and integrated into the digital twin by DTT, see Figure 22.

Figure 21 Occupancy Detection Process

⁸ LGBM (Light Gradient Boosting Machine) is an ensemble learning method that uses gradient boosting frameworks. It is known for its efficiency and speed, without compromising model accuracy.

Figure 22 Snapshot of the Safety Management Tool, SMT

7 ON-SITE RISK DETECTION ASSESSMENT

7.1 4D BIM scheduling and visualization

Utilizing 4D BIM scheduling, which extends from a foundational 3D BIM model by integrating temporal and spatial dimensions facilitates enhanced construction planning in complex construction projects (Fischer et al., 2003). The incorporation of the temporal dimension into the 3D BIM model allows for the mapping of construction activities over time (Boje et al., 2020). This enables a detailed analysis of the construction sequencing, enabling improved preparation and execution strategies across a production timeplan, through an integration of Construction Site Planning (CSP). Such an approach can be particularly beneficial in assessing construction site planning alternatives in regard to construction site safety, strategically scheduling high-risk activities with the objective of risk minimization, and proactively enhancing site safety during the planning phase (Zhou et al., 2013). The further inclusion of spatial scheduling ensures precise and optimal location-based approach on the allocation of resources at the construction site, especially during dangerous construction tasks, and supports comprehensive risk assessments based on simulated planned activities (ibid). 4D BIM scheduling could further also include historical data in the analysis and assessment integrated into the 3D model of the intended construction site (ibid).

Moreover, the selected 4D BIM framework with integrated an CSP can be continuously evaluated against the construction workflow and activities throughout the construction process, see Figure 23. This comparison enables the identification of discrepancies from the CSP, thereby elevating control and insight over the construction process through monitoring procedures. Proactive assessment of each construction activity, including coordination of activities with regards to risks among the multiple construction site trades, is a critical aspect of this integrated approach. 4D visualization and sequencing can be used to communicate risks within the parameters of the set construction plan to all stakeholders within the construction site, enhancing communication across workers and project managers (Sulankivi and Kiviniemi, 2010; Zhou et al., 2013). Further, as construction sites are dynamic and always changing, incorporating safety considerations proactively in the planning states can also include temporary structures as well as equipment (ibid). To this end, utilizing various real-time data collection methods from sensors as mentioned in chapter 6 during construction can aid in ensuring the 4D BIM scheduling is followed. Presented in the following section are methods of data collection on-site which can support the 4D BIM scheduling process.

Figure 23 Construction site planning, CSP, incorporated into the BIM model for effective planning and execution.

7.2 Methods to aggregate data on health and safety behavior towards site specific and company specific safety culture indicators

There exist a number of ways of collecting health and safety data from the construction site, from traditional analog note-taking to more advanced digital software registration. At NCC, the accumulated accident data uses a common method for registering and analyzing single occurrences of accidents in the construction industry. The case company's data are mostly gathered by safety engineers, site managers, safety representatives, and workers. Accidents are registered through a digital software interface called "Synergi Life", which is a complete quality, health, and safety risk management software package.

The software package offers the option of recording four types of reports:

- Accident: An event that led to personal injury.
- Incident: An unwanted, sudden event that could have led to a personal injury.
- Negative observation: An unwanted situation or risk that could have led to personal injury.
- Positive observation: A positive action or solution that has led to better health or safety.

This data is analyzed on a project level as well as on a business area and company level where the findings are presented in graphs and pie charts for following-up. Figure 24 shows a typical follow-up slide, in this case for accidents by days of absence, a company specific safety culture indicator.

Figure 24 Accidents per days of absence follow-up for understanding long-term effects of different measures and initiatives on a company level (Source: NCC)

This analysis is often complemented with a root-cause analysis on a project level to further develop the H&S work. However, with the advancement of machine learning and AI, a Ph.D. project was initiated to examine if further knowledge could be extracted from the data base. The midterm achievements were reported in Shayboun (2022). This work is continuing and currently a Q&A system process is being developed, see Figures 25 and 26. This opens up the possibility for safety engineers to gain a deeper understanding of dangerous situations and to scale best practices that would otherwise be difficult to spread outside the specific project.

Figure 25 Simplified question & answering system process for extracting value from H&S accident reporting system (Shayboun, M., personal communication 2024)

```
In [*]: # Your query
query = input("Din fråga här: ")# Replace with your query
```

Din fråga här: Translation: "Falls in scaffolding works?"

Document 1
Document 2
Document 3
Document 4

```
query = "vilken typ av skador finns i vårt material?"
```

Translation: "What types of injuries can be found in our material?"

Document 1 answer : benbrott (broken leg)
 Document 2 answer : revbenskada (rib injury)
 Document 3 answer : klämskada (crushing injury)
 Document 4 answer : personskador (personal injury)

Figure 26 Preliminary example of possible outcomes of database query (Shayboun, personal communication 2024)

8 ASSESSMENT OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES TO ENHANCE SAFETY ON CONSTRUCTION

This part of the deliverable aims to address how the construction industry is currently approaching the integration of real-time safety technologies into construction sites. The objective is to examine the use and implementation of real-time safety and accident prevention technologies in the construction industry, the attitude and perspectives of industry professionals towards the use of these technologies, and the potential barriers and challenges of their implementation in the construction industry. Most of the results build on a master thesis (Stenbäck Jurich, 2023), supervised by ASHVIN partner PlanB, and was limited to a Swedish context.

8.1 Three key themes

Seven semi-structured interviews were conducted with professionals active in the construction sector in Sweden, with a specific focus on those who had experience within digitalization. Most participants represented large construction companies. To provide additional insight, two individuals from the construction industry with expertise in workplace health and safety were also interviewed. The interviews were conducted in Swedish over Microsoft Teams and were scheduled for 60 minutes time. The aim of the semi-structured interviews was to gain a deeper understanding of the construction sector's view and knowledge regarding digitalization and innovative technologies with safety features in the sector. Further, it was to examine the sector interest, challenges and needs regarding the implementation of innovative digital solutions or methods which aim to increase the safety for construction workers.

From the interview data three key themes were identified:

- (1) *The use of technology to increase safety on construction sites,*
- (2) *Barriers to implementing technology,*
- (3) *The need for a long-term strategy and collaboration.*

Fel! Hittar inte referenskölla. provides an overview of the themes and sub-themes used in the study.

Figure 27 Thematic analysis of results

8.1.1 Theme one: The use of technology to increase safety on construction sites

Theme one of the study focuses on the use, the current state of adoption, and the implementation of real-time safety technologies in the construction industry. The findings reveal that the use of digital technologies to enhance safety on construction sites is still in its early stages. However, specific technologies and solutions, such as IoT and sensor technology, were identified as having great potential for use on construction sites to increase safety. The respondents mentioned different safety benefits of using technologies at construction sites, such as increasing awareness of potential hazards and alerting construction workers of such hazards. Many interviewees believe that the use of digital methods to increase safety on construction sites will increase in the future, and that it will become more common to use techniques such as sensors and automated processes.

8.1.2 Theme two: Barriers to implementing digital safety technology

The second theme pertains to the various barriers that may arise in the implementation and use of various safety technologies on construction sites. These barriers include technical difficulties and challenges associated with identifying and integrating appropriate technology, as well as the need for testing and validation. Additionally, financial constraints and concerns related to the monitoring of employees and the workplace also represent potential barriers.

The findings from the data in theme two showed that it can be difficult to find a suitable technology that is adapted to the construction industry and to the specific conditions

on a construction site. It can also be hard to convince the decision-makers about the benefits of using the technologies, as there is uncertainty about the profitability of these technologies and they can involve high investment costs. Additionally, the industry's focus on low costs and the short-term thinking is another concern. The respondents had mixed opinions on the use of monitoring technology to enhance safety on construction sites due to the surveillance and privacy aspects.

These mixed opinions regarding privacy in the Swedish context also relate to findings of T6.5, which showed that concerns about the invasiveness of privacy in safety technology in construction are highly context dependent. For instance, in a Turkish context, workers emphasized the contribution of surveillance technologies not only to enhance worker safety but also to understand why accidents happen when they cannot be prevented. In turn, workers in Spain were more focused on the potential 'function creep' of these monitoring technologies, specifically, that they would be used for purposes other than safety, such as assessing productivity or controlling workers. These findings strongly suggest that barriers to digital safety technology are highly context-dependent, and that cultural characteristics play a key role in determining adoption.

8.1.3 Theme three: The need for a long-term strategy and collaboration

Theme three of the thematic analysis focuses on the integration of technology in the construction industry, specifically the need for collaboration and the exploration of new business models to effectively incorporate technology in the construction process.

The findings from the data in theme three of the thematic analysis highlights the need for collaboration, finding new business models, and the need of involving tech-companies in a long-term strategy for developing, testing and integrating technology in the construction industry. The respondents believed that it can be difficult to convince various stakeholders of the necessity of new technology, and that there may exist a lack of understanding or knowledge among industry professionals about the potential benefits and capabilities of these technologies. Furthermore, the findings also stress that there are many different stakeholders and actors that influence the work environment and safety.

8.2 Reflections on specific technologies and potential benefits

According to the respondents, real-time connected methods on construction sites can contribute to increased safety by allowing the avoidance and minimization of risks and incidents, and quickly obtaining information about accidents that may occur and providing aid and assistance to people. These solutions may include tracking individuals and machinery, automatic warning systems in potentially hazardous situations, and digital safety barriers. Real-time monitoring systems, such as wearables, sensors, and cameras to track the location and movements of workers on site was one of the main technology areas mentioned by the respondents. These systems can alert workers and supervisors to potential hazards, such as the proximity of heavy machines or other risks, and can help to prevent accidents by giving enough time to react and take appropriate action.

8.3 Identifying and addressing obstacles with new technologies

Many respondents mentioned the cost of purchasing and maintaining new technologies as a concern. It was also noted by several respondents that it can be challenging to persuade decision-makers to introduce new technologies on construction sites, particularly when large investments are needed. The difficulty in demonstrating the long-term benefits of the technology may contribute to this challenge. The findings suggest that in construction, projects are often temporary, and the focus is on immediate benefits rather than long-term planning. Many respondents reported that it can be difficult to demonstrate the immediate benefits of a decision to stakeholders, leading to a lack of investment in technology. These findings highlight the construction industry's tendency to prioritize cost reduction rather than prioritizing safety measures. This hesitation to invest in safety technologies may be due to the large investment required.

According to the respondents, there were some technical challenges in terms of ensuring that the technology will function effectively on the construction site. While the respondent noted this as a possible concern and noted that some more testing is necessary to ensure that the technology functions properly, it was not as prominent as the cultural and organizational barriers that were mentioned. Furthermore, it was highlighted by some respondents that improvements to connectivity are necessary to use real-time safety technologies on construction sites.

The respondents had mixed opinions on the use of monitoring technology to enhance safety on construction sites. Some respondents mentioned that they view this type of technology with some skepticism, and that they may be concerned that it can be used to unnecessarily intrusively monitor and control employees and create a sense that you are constantly being surveilled on the construction site (Figure 28). While other respondents didn't see the monitoring as an obstacle or a problem if it is clearly communicated and seen as a tool to increase safety. However, since the implementation of these types of technology used for safety management involves collecting personal data, it is essential that the employer ensures compliance with the privacy and data protection regulations. Furthermore, it is important to consider these privacy concerns when evaluating the usefulness and feasibility of new technologies as in some cases strict limitations on data collection may significantly diminish the effectiveness of a technology (JRC, 2019).

Figure 28 Some of the interviewees noted that “unnecessarily intrusively monitor and control employees and create a sense that you are constantly being surveilled” (Image source: EU-OSHA, 2018)

8.4 Organizational Challenges that need to be addressed

The respondents mentioned resistance to change and the traditional culture of the construction sector. There is a tendency to stick with tried and tested methods making it difficult to introduce new technology. This aligns with previous observations that the construction sector tends to resist change (Oesterreich & Teuteberg, 2016). Furthermore, the data collected suggest that the adoption and implementation of new technology in the construction industry is challenged by the lack of understanding and expertise among decision makers and a general tendency towards caution in the industry. This perspective aligns with the findings of Lawrence and Scanlan (2007), who propose that organizations may be resistant to change and may find it difficult to adopt new technologies due to their familiarity with established tools and processes. This presents challenges for the implementation of new technologies in the industry. In addition to the aforementioned factors, the degree of radicalism of the innovation may also contribute to the slow adoption of new technology, according to Welch et al. (2015) the more radical and disruptive an innovation is, the less likely it is for the technology to be adapted.

Another challenge mentioned was difficulties in coordination and collaboration between different stakeholders as the construction industry is typically characterized by complex and dynamic project structures with multiple stakeholders involved. The collaboration issues and a lack of coordination between stakeholders also aligns with previous research on the challenges of adoption of new technology (Crocker and

Rowlinson, 2007). The literature suggests that organizational culture and structure play a vital role in the integration of new technologies and the need for strong leadership and communication to facilitate this change and overcome resistance (Sargent et al., 2012; Talukder, 2012).

The respondents all mentioned the need for construction companies to collaborate with tech-companies in order to ensure profitability and sustainability in the long run and that it can be difficult to establish a long-term strategy to get all parties to cooperate and participate in the process. The literature also emphasized the importance of a digital ecosystem and the need for collaboration between different parties (Gartner, 2017).

9 DISCUSSION

In this work, the focus has been on real-time safety technologies in the construction industry. A user-centric framework aiming for keeping everyone safe at the construction site has been proposed. The framework shows how the physical object (the construction site), and the digital twin intervene in order to allow data to be collected and used to increase safety on site. However, the objectives have also been to examine the use cases and implementation of real-time safety technologies in the construction industry and the attitude and perspectives of industry professionals towards these technologies.

In the realm of improving the safety on construction sites with the use of digital technologies, the implementation of sensors and the Internet of Things (IoT) is expected to be significant. According to a report from the European commission (2021) regarding digitalization in the construction sector, sensors represent the main source of real-time data and are a central part for the future construction industry (European Commission, 2021).

The literature review, online research, and small-scale tests confirm that several safety technologies for construction have reached market maturity. This shows that there exist technologies which can be used for safety and accident prevention application on construction sites.

The findings of this study suggest that the use of digital technologies to enhance safety on construction sites appears to be a nascent field. In the interviews carried out by Stenbäck Juhrich (2023), none of the respondents had any plans to adopt these for safety purposes nor did they use any today, but all of the respondents saw the potential benefits from using the technologies. Up to now, the main focus on using digital technologies in construction has been on the early stages of the building process with emphasis on productivity and efficiency, not in the construction phase. Our findings indicate that there is currently a lack of focus on using digital technologies to increase safety in construction, but there are a variety of prototypes being developed and tested. However, there appears to be a need to increase attention and focus on safety and digital technologies within the construction industry. The data collected from interviews suggest that many believe digitalization could be a key factor in promoting safety within the construction sector. This aligns with the findings in the literature, which also suggest that these technologies may play a significant role in future safety solutions on construction sites (Okpala and Nnaji, 2020; Zhang et al., 2017). Furthermore, a gap between what is currently available and what is being used in the industry was identified. To guarantee that the technology operates correctly at construction sites, it needs to undergo further testing in a real construction environment. Better and more reliant connectivity is required in order to achieve a real-time connected construction site. It appears as the construction industry does not face any main technical barriers to implementing real-time safety technologies. Instead, the challenges are organizational and cultural. Both the literature and the respondents emphasize the importance of involving tech-companies and collaborating with other stakeholders in the development and testing process. Findings from this study suggest that larger construction companies have begun to find their collaborative partners, which may include start-ups, small businesses, and larger tech-companies. These partnerships

and networks have enabled them to work together and drive the development of new technology. However, it seems that a successful (business) model has not yet been established, which have hindered construction companies from more actively pursuing development.

Although it is acknowledged that the implementation of real-time safety technologies will be expensive, there is uncertainty about whether there will be any financial gain in addition to the increased safety on the construction site. Construction companies often prioritize cost savings over safety, which can lead to safety risks on the job site. According to a three-year longitudinal study by Oswald et al. (2020), construction companies often compromise safety in favor of cost savings through cost-saving measures in equipment, workers, and investments in a safe working environment. The study suggests that going for a low-cost option for safety equipment and resources might not be the wisest choice. Hiring cheaper, less experienced or migrant workers could end up being more expensive in the long run due to the need for additional safety management. Spending more on safety can actually lead to cost saving in the long run.

This was highlighted by López-Alonso et al. (2013) who found that the average number of accidents on construction projects decreases as the cost of accident prevention increases. The authors also noted that cost increases with the size of the project. The cost of accidents is directly related to the number of workers and sub-contractors and is higher when there are more workers and sub-contractors. In a study conducted by Ikpe et al. (2012), which focused on the financial impacts of health and safety management in the construction sector, it was found that the benefits of preventing accidents far outweighed the cost. The results showed that the benefits are about three times greater than the cost, indicating that investing in health and safety also has cost-saving benefits.

10 CONCLUSIONS

The construction industry is currently experiencing a technological revolution that promises to redefine safety standards. Advancements in AI, IoT, and machine learning are transforming the methodologies and tools available for ensuring safety on construction sites. AI algorithms can continuously monitor live video feeds from construction sites, identifying safety violations in real-time and notifying supervisors or other relevant personnel. These technologies are becoming more accessible, making them a practical option for smaller construction firms or projects with limited budgets. This democratization of technology means that every construction project can benefit from the highest safety standards made possible by the latest technological innovations. However, while the possibilities are endless, this type of technology is currently met with some scepticism by site personnel. They express concern that the technologies can monitor and control employees in an overly intrusive manner, creating a sense that one is constantly being surveilled on the construction site. Thus, specific care is needed when designing the tools to incorporate privacy aspects.

In our work, we have designed a framework to support the traditional safety measures with digital technologies, allowing the physical and the digital twins to co-exist and support each other in order to provide the actors in the building process with decision support to increase on-site safety. Safety does not start on the construction sites but needs to be incorporated already in the design process. In this deliverable, we have illustrated how to introduce construction safety already in the design phase through the use of virtual reality (VR). We have illustrated what a digital on-boarding could look like, regardless of preferred language, to ensure that all workers have sufficient knowledge before entering the site. Other examples include detection of personnel in risk zones, identification of individuals on-site persons outside of working hours, and protection gear verification. Lastly, we conducted a series of interviews to gain insights into the current perceptions, challenges, and opportunities associated with the use of digital technologies on construction sites. This information is crucial for understanding how these technologies can be effectively implemented to improve safety and efficiency in the construction industry.

One barrier identified in both interviews and literature is the complex and dynamic project structure and the involvement of multiple stakeholders. The increase in the number of involved stakeholders in a project naturally requires greater cooperation and clear communication. Any shortcomings in this regard can create obstacles for multiple stakeholders. On the other hand, this may also be an opportunity for the construction industry to find a good model for cooperation and to realize that more people involved in the process means more knowledge to share, more risks and costs to share. Thus, the large number of stakeholders involved could be a benefit. Finding a model for cooperation not only enables the development of these technologies to progress and the sharing of risks. It may also serve as a way to promote cooperation throughout the entire construction project between the various stakeholders involved. Further work is needed in this area.

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APPENDIX A Typical literature references for the state-of-the industry in Chapter 2

Source	Contents
<p>Wu, Shaoze, et al. "Real-time mixed reality-based visual warning for construction workforce safety." <i>Automation in Construction</i> 139 (2022): 104252.</p>	<p>This paper integrates Digital Twin (DT), Deep Learning (DL), and Mixed Reality (MR) technologies into a newly developed real-time visual warning system, which enables construction workers to proactively determine their safety status and avoid accidents</p>
<p>Ye, Zijian, et al. "A digital twin approach for tunnel construction safety early warning and management." <i>Computers in Industry</i> 144 (2023): 103783.</p>	<p>This paper proposes a digital twin based multi-information intelligent early warning and safety management platform for tunnel construction</p>
<p>Li, Beidi, et al. "Towards digital twins for knowledge-driven construction progress and predictive safety analysis on a construction site." <i>Leveraging Applications of Formal Methods, Verification and Validation: Tools and Trends: 9th International Symposium on Leveraging Applications of Formal Methods, ISoLA 2020, Rhodes, Greece, October 20–30, 2020, Proceedings, Part IV 9</i>. Springer International Publishing, 2021.</p>	<p>This paper provides a vision of how digital twins can assist with spotting potential violations of the constraints stated by the rules and regulations, and empirically evaluate a proof-of-concept software tool on a large scale, real-world 4D BIM.</p>
<p>Hou, Lei, et al. "Literature review of digital twins applications in construction workforce safety." <i>Applied Sciences</i> 11.1 (2020): 339.</p>	<p>In order to understand the research advances of sensing and visualisation technologies, identify their gaps and challenges, and propose solutions to further advance the industry's safety, this paper provides a thorough review on the state-of-the-art technological studies, and elaborates upon the key findings in detail.</p>
<p>Saini, Gurtej Singh, et al. "Digital Twins for Real-Time Scenario Analysis during Well Construction Operations." <i>Energies</i> 15.18 (2022): 6584.</p>	<p>While there are approaches and tools to monitor well construction operations, there are none that evaluate potential action sequences and scenarios and select the best possible sequence of actions. This paper defines a generalized iterative methodology for setting up a digital twin to address this shortcoming.</p>
<p>Diange, Sun, and Ni Haiyun. "Research on the Construction of Civil Airport Safety Management System Based on Digital Twin Technology." <i>2022 IEEE 13th International Conference on Software Engineering and Service Science (ICSESS)</i>. IEEE, 2022.</p>	<p>This paper discusses the feasibility of using digital twin technology to build a civil airport safety management system and provides a design framework.</p>
<p>Talmaki, Sanat A., and Kamat, Vineet R.. "Sensor Acquisition and Allocation for Real-Time Monitoring of Articulated Construction Equipment in Digital Twins." <i>Sensors</i> 22.19 (2022): 7635.</p>	<p>This paper develops a scalable technical approach and presents a prototype application framework for transmitting real world sensor data to update 3D equipment models inside a graphical digital twin for concurrent visualization of a monitored construction operation</p>
<p>Liu, Zhan-Sheng, et al. "Digital twin-based intelligent safety risks prediction of prefabricated construction hoisting." <i>Sustainability</i> 14.9 (2022): 5179.</p>	<p>This paper proposes an intelligent safety risk prediction framework of prefabricated construction hoisting, in order to predict the</p>

	hoisting risk in real-time and investigate the spatial-temporal evolution law of the risk
Chronopoulos, Christos, et al. "Towards a Holistic, Self-Organised Safety Framework for Construction." 2021 IEEE International Conference on Autonomic Computing and Self-Organizing Systems Companion (ACSOS-C). IEEE, 2021.	This paper outlines a framework incorporating multi-modal sensory information into digital twins in construction sites. The construction plan is enriched in the digital twin during runtime with additional information such as work plans, identified and mitigated hazard zones, and current location of workers, resources, and mobile equipment. Utilising this information in the digital twin allows executing simulations to predict potentially dangerous situations for workers.

APPENDIX B - Summary of Safety Technologies

Technology	Purpose	Study
BLE technology was attached to construction workers' hardhat & equipment to	Monitor dangerous proximity between workers and equipment in real-time at outdoor construction site. Send out tactile alerts to workers, help to maintain a safe distance	Huang et al. (2021). <i>Automation in Construction</i> (132).
Bluetooth device attached to workers hardhat	Real time tracking to find factors that influence non helmet use on construction sites	Li et al. (2017). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 80, 95-103.
Wearable Inertial Measurement Units attached to workers ankle	Monitoring workers walking patterns to identify risks of falling at construction sites	Yang et al. (2017). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 82, 166-178.
Passive RFID tag attached to workers' hard hats at an outdoor construction site	Proximity detection and warning system in order to prevent collision between equipment and workers	Teizer (2015). <i>Journal of Information Technology in Construction</i> (20), 295-312.
UWB technology for real-time location system	Track crane movement on construction site to predict potential collisions & prevent crashes. Provide support to crane operators on construction site.	Zhang et al. (2012). <i>Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering</i> , 26(5), 625-637.
Integrated system using Computer Vision and GPS real time location system.	Locating and positioning of excavators at construction sites.	Soltani et al. (2018). <i>Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering</i> , 32(6).
Building Information Model (BIM) and BLE location technology	BLE used to track workers' positions in real-time. BIM used to automatically or manually define hazardous areas. If worker is in hazardous area and alert is sent out to worker and manager	Park et al. (2017). <i>Journal of Construction Engineering and Management</i> , 143(2).
Integrated vision-based monitoring system using CCTV camera to monitor the construction site and moving objects and vision data from wearable devices equipped on worker	Hazard identification system. The safety information is presented to workers in the wearable device using augmented reality.	Kim et al. (2017). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 83, 390-403.
Computer Vision. Utilized cameras installed on heavy construction equipment	real-time hazard identification of collision accidents between workers and heavy equipment on construction sites	Son et al. (2019). <i>Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering</i> , 33(5).
Building Information Model (BIM) and RFID-based monitoring system to track workers	System automatically identifies hazards by comparing the optimal/shortest path based on BIM objects and the actual route workers are taking	Kim et al. (2016). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 65, 21-32.
GPS aided inertial navigation system (INS) sensor used for tracking. Extended Kalman filter (EKF) and the nearest-neighbor method to estimate the position, direction and speed of the objects	Unsafe proximity detection system with reduced false alarms by incorporating the position, direction and speed of objects (equipment and workers) on construction sites in real-time	Wang & Razavi (2016). <i>Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering</i> , 30(2).
Audio-based system, using microphones installed at the construction site; machine learning was used to analyze the data	System to analyze the activity and tracking construction equipment	Cheng et al. (2017). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 81, 240-253.

Active RFID	Proximity warning system outdoor between workers and heavy equipment construction sites	Chae & Yoshida (2010). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , (19), 368-374.
Ultra-high frequency passive RFID (low cost)	indoor material and worker tracking in near real-time at construction site	Montaser & Moselhi (2014). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 39, 167-179.
GPS for worker and equipment localization, IMUs for head orientation, UWB technology to send alert to workers	proximity warning system at construction sites incorporate workers' awareness to decrease the number of false alarms triggered in safe conditions	Chan et al. (2020). <i>Sensors</i> 2020, 20(3), 806
Virtual construction simulation system (VCS) where a 3D model of a construction site, surrounding environments & position of hazardous zones are stored. Location of workers, equipment and vehicles on site transmitted to VCS in real-time	When a worker is situated in close proximity to a hazardous area, a warning is sent to the workers and the incident is reported and saved in the system for future training	Li et al. (2015). <i>Safety Science</i> (75), 107-117.
Deep learning-based computer vision: Mask Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network (R-CNN)	Automatically detect construction workers who move on structural support without proper safety gear	Fang et al. (2019). <i>Advanced Engineering Informatics</i> , 39, 170-177.
Deep learning-based computer vision: Region-Based Convolutional Neural Network (Faster R-CNN)	Automatically detect individuals not wearing protective hardhats on construction sites	Fang et al. (2018). <i>Automation in Construction</i> , 85, 1-9.
UWB technology for a Real-Time Location System	Used to track heavy equipment at outdoor construction sites	Siddiqui et al. (2019). <i>Journal of Information Technology in Construction</i> , 24, 167-187.